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AI as a socio-technical system for care

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a socio-technical system holds promise for enhancing caregiving. The "ToiletHelp" system exemplifies this by using AI to assist users during toilet use, improving safety and efficiency. However, integrating AI in care settings raises significant ethical challenges, including risks of depersonalization, bias, and the potential dehumanization of care. A robust governance model ensures fairness, transparency, and accountability. The successful implementation of AI in care requires technological innovation and careful consideration of ethical, social, and practical implications to serve best all stakeholders involved.

AI system

Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a socio-technical system offers transformative potentials in care, particularly by facilitating the daily work of caregivers, enhancing the safety of those in need, and contributing significantly to the health and well-being of users. Technologies, integrated within care environments, aim to increase the productivity of care activities and reduce the long-term costs associated with rapid demographic changes.

One such technology is "ToiletHelp" [1], which uses a rule-based engine and convolutional neural network to detect difficulties in toilet's use for people with

dementia. ToiletHelp utilizes depth maps to analyze the scene and determine if the user requires assistance. Depending on the user's current action, the system predicts the subsequent step and awaits the user's completion. Should the user encounter difficulties, ToiletHelp activates both video and verbal instructions to assist the user in proceeding to the next action [2].

Figure 1 ToiletHelp in a care center [1]. User interaction sequence with ToiletHelp. a) Recognition of the user next to the toilet, prompting them to sit. b) User follows the prompt. c) Confirmation message reassures the user

Figure 1 illustrates the ToiletHelp system installed in a restroom. The device, a white edge device equipped with an integrated depth sensor, is mounted at an elevated position on the wall or ceiling to ensure a comprehensive view of the room, covering both the toilet bowl and the washbasin. An interaction device, consisting of a monitor coupled with a speaker, is strategically placed to be easily visible to the user. ToiletHelp processes information through four principal components: the depth sensor, the scene recognition module, the action recognition module, and the interaction module.

Governance of AI in Care

However, the integration of AI in care settings comes with its own set of challenges and ethical considerations. Risks such as the depersonalization of care through algorithm-based standardization, discrimination against minority groups due to biased algorithms, the dehumanization of care relationships through automation, and coercive control of users through surveillance technologies need careful consideration. These ethical risks require a robust governance model that ensures AI applications in healthcare are fair, trustworthy, and accountable.

The governance of AI in health care should include data governance panels to oversee data collection and usage, ensuring that AI models are designed to uphold

procedural and distributive justice [3]. It is essential to educate both caregivers and patients about the functionalities and limitations of AI, ensuring fully informed consent is obtained for the use of such technologies. Furthermore, AI applications must be regulated at various stages—approval, introduction, and deployment—to ensure accountability and transparency in decision-making processes.

AI systems in care are part of complex networks that include material infrastructures such as sensors and the care infrastructure, as well as human activities and organizational practices. Different stakeholders—developers, caregivers, managers, and residents—bring diverse perspectives to the use of technology in care, influencing its development and implementation.

Care work itself is a complex network that necessitates an interdisciplinary approach, combining insights from care, technology, law, and social sciences to tackle the legal, cultural, and practical challenges associated with AI. Questions about who defines risky behaviors and what criteria lead to someone being labeled fall-prone are crucial. These discussions extend to the transparency and fairness of AI systems, particularly how behaviors are classified and the implications for those in care.

As primary users of these AI systems, older adults must be actively considered in the development processes. How older individuals perceive, understand, and interact with AI systems is fundamental to the design of these technologies. Ensuring that AI systems are understandable and explainable across different levels of technological competence among older adults is vital for their acceptance and efficacy.

The practical challenges of implementing technologies in care settings demand consideration not only of their technical aspects but also of their social implications. Legal assessments are needed to determine the classification of data used, while acknowledging cultural and regional differences in technology acceptance is crucial to ensure a comprehensive and inclusive approach to AI in care.

In conclusion, AI as a socio-technical system in care settings represents a promising frontier with the potential to enhance care quality and efficiency. However, it also demands careful consideration of ethical, social, and practical aspects to ensure that technology serves the best interests of all stakeholders involved.

References

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